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The application of geostatistics based model for the phosphate mineral resource estimation in a dry climate region, case of the Bled El Hadba phosphate deposit, NE Algeria

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Abstract

Since many decades, several researchers have been exploring the potential of geostatistics in mineral resource estimation, resulting in numerous works and publications. The Bled El Hadba phosphate deposit, of the Jebel Onk mining basin, NE Algeria is structured in a basal, a principal, and a summit sublayer. A total of 24 core holes were drilled with a mesh size of 400*300m. We analyzed the exploration data with a Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The results of the correlation circles of the loading factors on the chemical elements P₂O₅, CaO, mgO, SiO₂, Fe₂O₃, CO₂, and IR (Insoluble Residue) allowed us, the identification of three main associations: the first association is formed by P₂O₅ and CaO representing the phosphate material; the second association is that of mgO and CO₂ representing the dolomitic gangue; and the third association is made up of SiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and IR representing the siliceous clay gangue. This study proves that the PCA model can accommodate drilling geological parameters and effectively approximate complex relationships among them. The variography of P₂O₅ contents allows the construction of a geostatistics model of the distribution of phosphate resources in each of these constituent sublayers. The geostatic simulation provided several possible variants, one of which could be the closest to reality. The latter would allow the most rigorous planning and control of the exploitation. Our approach could be applied in similar deposits with the same deposition conditions throughout the region.

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Introduction

Sedimentary phosphates represent an important resource for their multiple uses in agriculture and industry. Algeria is like the countries of North Africa, contains large quantities concentrated in the mining basin of Djebel Onk in Tébessa, where five phosphate deposits have been discovered. These deposits contain more than two billion tons of resources. Among these deposits the deposit of Bled El Hadba which is the object of our study. The Bled El Hadba phosphate deposit is located in the Djebel Onk basin, 14 km south-east of Bir-El-Ater, Tébessa (Fig. 1). The geological studies (e.g. Ranchin, 1963; Cielensky & Benchermine, 1987; Prian & Cortiel, 1993; Mezghacheet *et al.*, 2002; 2004) showed that the phosphate bed is composed of three sub-layers: the basal, the principal, and the summit sub-layers. Each of these sub-layers exhibits specific mineralogical and geochemical characteristics. Therefore, it is essential to separately valorize them. The geostatistical estimate by ordinary kriging allows the modeling of a deposit (Kechiched, 2011, Boulemia *et al.*, 2021) but it does not reproduce the "histogram and variogram"

characteristics of the variable. It therefore provides a simplified image of the phenomenon studied. Hence the interest of using another approach: the simulation, which makes it possible to consider several variants, has the same statistical and spatial characteristics as reality and therefore optimizes planning and operation, which is the objective of our study. This simulation was performed by sequential Gaussian Simulation Method (SGS) of the phosphate resources of each of the three sub-layers. The obtained results were provided in the present work.

Materials and methods

Geological Setting

The Bled El Hadba phosphate deposit is a sedimentary deposit. The beds age ranges from Thanetian to Quaternary. The phosphate bed is of Upper Thanetian age (Fig. 1). This layer is subdivided into three sublayers: the basal, the principal, and the summit sub-layers. The phosphate layer is about 30 m thick. Its exploration was carried out by many exploration campaigns. In total 720 samples were taken from the 24 drillings.

Fig. 1. Geologic location map of the study area 1: Alluvial deposit, 2: deposit composed of fallen limestones, quartz, sands and clays, 3: Limestones with silex of Ypresian age, 4: phosphate layer of Thanetian age, 5: schistosed marls and clays of Lower Thanetian age, 6: limestones and marls of Montian age, 7: trench, 8: well (EREM, 1987).

Used methods

Methods of multivariate data analysis

The principal component analysis PCA is a method of multivariate data processing. The principal of this method is described by many authors (Lebart *et al.*, 1979; Benzecrit *et al.*, 1980; Volle, 1981). It is commonly used in the earth sciences field (Mezghache, 1989). It is a factorial method that allows constructing factors considered as new independent variables or not correlated statistically and facilitating the study between the initial variables. The main objective is to extract, in a condensate form, the largest amount possible of information contained in the data. Be it connected to the relationships between variables or individuals. The main steps for a PCA are:

- The calculation the correlation matrix and search of load factors.
- Plotting interpretation of correlations circles.
- And finally probably mapping individual's factors.

Geostatistical methods

Geostatistics or regionalized variables theory aims to study the random functions. (Matheron, 1965-1970) introduced the regionalized variables notion to quantify a random phenomenon showing a spatial variability structure. The geostatistical modeling was already studied in a number of geological research works (Goovaerts, 1997; Deutsch, 2002; Leuangthong *et al.*, 2004; Daniel Khan *et al.*, 2008; Cabello, 2009). In our work, the geostatistical method used is the Sequential Gaussian simulation method SGS.

Sequential Gaussian Simulation- SGS

The simulation aims to generate by adequate algorithms multiple realizations of the random function Z(x). By construction, these constructions are all equiprobable and have the same statistical and spatial characteristics that the reality z(x).

Two main geostatistical simulations: Gaussian and non-Gaussian. In our work, the simulation was carried out by means of a Gaussian method: the Sequential Gaussian Simulation SGS. It is applied on the observations following a Gaussian law. If the distribution is not Gaussian, a transformation of the

variable into a Gaussian variable Y is necessary. This is an anamorphosis.

* The steps of this simulation method are (Kedzierski, 2007):

- Choosing a grid node and defining a search sphere in the case of the isotropic phenomenon or a search ellipsoid in the case of anisotropy;
- Kriging a value to this point Zo (x);
- Constructing a Gaussian law from the kriging estimate and the variance estimate at a node;
- Drawing a random value from this distribution;
- Adding the simulated value to the available values list.

Results and discussion

Multivariate data analysis PCA

The core samples were analyzed for the chemical elements P₂O₅, CaO, mgO, SiO₂, Fe₂O₃, CO₂ and IR.

The simple correlation matrix (Table. 1) was computed on the geochemical data of the core samples taken from the principal sub-layer. This matrix shows that:

- P₂O₅ is positively correlated with CaO, negatively with CO₂, RI, mgO, SiO₂;
- CO₂ is positively correlated with mgO, negatively with Fe₂O₃ and CaO;
- IR is positively correlated with Fe₂O₃ and mgO is negatively correlated with SiO₂;
- mgO is negatively correlated with CaO and mgO;
- Fe₂O₃ is positively correlated with SiO₂ and CaO is negatively correlated with SiO₂.

Table 1. Correlation matrix of chemical elements.

	P ₂ O ₅	CO ₂	RI	MgO	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	SiO ₂
P ₂ O ₅	1,00						
CO ₂	-0,75*	1,00					
RI	-0,17*	-0,12	1,00				
MgO	-0,79*	0,88*	-0,07	1,00			
Fe ₂ O ₃	0,01	-0,23*	0,71*	-0,18*	1,00		
CaO	0,40*	-0,42*	-0,31*	-0,50*	-0,13	1,00	
SiO ₂	-0,16*	-0,14	0,98*	-0,09	0,73*	-0,28*	1,00

*: significant correlations

From the correlation simple linear matrix (Table 1), the load factors were computed (Table 2). This table indicates that 90.44% of data is provided by the first

three factors: 41.98% of data is provided by the load factor F1, 39.56% by the factor F2 and 8.9% by the factor F3.

These computed load factors aim to plot the correlations circles (Fig. 2). The graphical correlations-representation circles of the relationships loads factors/chemical elements allowed to determine the major associations (Fig. 2):

- The first association is formed by P_2O_5 and CaO: it is positively correlated with the factor F2 and negatively with the factor F1. It represents the phosphate matter;
- The second association is that of mgO and CO_2 : it is marked by a positive correlation with the factors F1 and F2. It represents the dolomitic gangue;
- The third association is constituted of SiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 and IR (insoluble residue): SiO_2 and IR are marked by a positive correlation with the factor F1 and a negative correlation with the factor F2. It represents the clayey-siliceous gangue.

Table 2. The load factors of chemical elements.

	F1	F2	F3
Variance (%)	41,98	39,56	8,90
P_2O_5	-0,88	0,12	-0,31
CO_2	0,92	0,19	0,12
RI	0,06	-0,96	0,04
MgO	0,95	0,12	0,07
Fe_2O_3	-0,13	-0,85	0,13
CaO	-0,63	0,34	0,69
SiO_2	0,03	-0,97	0,07

Fig. 2. Correlation circles on the contents of chemical elements.

Geostatistical simulation

The considered regionalized variable is the P_2O_5 content. The geostatistical study and the Sequential Gaussian Simulation method were carried out by means of the Petrel software in the three phosphate sub-layers.

Variography in the three phosphate sub-layers

The directional experimental variograms of the P_2O_5 contents in the three phosphate sub-layers were computed and adjusted (Table 3 and Fig. 3). The variography results indicate the presence of an isotropic structure; i.e. all the variograms practically exhibit the same ranges. These results were used for the simulation.

Table 3. Variography results in the three layers - Bled El Hadba deposit.

Designation	Directional variograms the major axis				Directional variograms the minor axis			
	a (m)	C_0 (% ²)	C (% ²)	Modèle	a (m)	C_0 (% ²)	C (% ²)	Model
Summit sublayer	1700	0.01	1.99	Spherical	1700	0.013	1.022	Spherical
Principal sublayer	1500	0	1.08	Spherical	1500	0.250	0.850	Spherical
Basal sublayer	1500	0	1.19	Spherical	1500	0	1.200	Spherical

Geostatistical simulation in the three phosphate sub-layers

The simulation by the sequential Gaussian method - SSG - was done in 3D. The different sub-layers, which are three in number, have been simulated. It made it possible to obtain four variants A, B, C and D for each sub-layer. Anisotropy has been taken into account in this simulation.

The maps of the three simulated sub-layers (Fig. 4) show that it is the variants of the main sub-layer which are the richest in phosphate with contents greater than 12%. On the other hand, the two other sub-layers basal and summit are relatively low potential areas. It should be noted that the summit sub-layers contain low potential sectors.

This is explained by the change of facies in the lateral plane. Simulation by the SGS method made it possible to obtain variants of the distribution of P_2O_5 resources in the three sub-layers One of them is the closest to reality.

Fig. 3. Calculation and adjustment of variograms in the three sub-layers: a-b: summitsub-layer, c-d: Principal sub-layer, e-f: Basal sub-layer

Fig. 4. Map of the results of the geostatistical simulation of the variable P₂O₅ in the three sub-layers. Four variants were simulated A, B, C and D.

Conclusion

The bearing horizon of the phosphate mineralisation is formed of a layer of Upper Thanetian age. It has an average thickness of 30 m. This layer outcrops in the eastern part of the deposit and dips north-west under the Ypresian limestones and the Miocene sediments. The phosphate layer is made up of the superposition of three sub-layers: summit sub-layer, principal sub-layer and basal sub-layer.

The principal component analysis PCA of data revealed the existence of three chemical associations that represent the phosphate matter, the dolomitic gangue and the clayey gangue. It also allowed for the computing of correlations between the different elements, thereby indicating that P_2O_5 is positively correlated with CaO, negatively with CO_2 , IR, mgO and SiO_2 . The geostatistical study and the simulation were carried out on the regionalized variable P_2O_5 . The directional experimental variograms of the P_2O_5 contents in the three phosphate sub-layers were computed and adjusted.

The results reveal the existence of an isotropic structure. The maps simulated by the SGS method allowed determining the most potential sectors in the three sub-layers.

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